

Design and Treatability Studies of Low-Cost Bio Filter In Water Treatment

Dr. Pranab Jyoti Barman*, Rhishikesh Gogoi, Muktar Ali, Wasim Zafar Islam

Department of Civil Engineering, Jorhat Institute of Science and Technology, Jorhat, Assam, India

ABSTRACT

In India, the water shortage is one of the major issues coming from the rural areas area which necessitates water treatment options. To address these issues in rural areas there is need for conceptualizing a treatment scheme to reduce cost. Water is a fundamental source to our existence. As cities expand and population grows, the demand for water is rising. With increase in population, there will be an increase in stress on sanitation and wastewater disposal system. The benefits of well-organized water management scheme is that it offers a tool for coping with water scarcity and reduces the amount of pollution which may enter in the hydrological cycle. Untreated water contains microorganisms, chemical contaminants and physical contaminants. Our study focuses on treatment of water using naturally available materials and to reduce pollutants in laboratory scale with the help of designed biofilters. In our study, we use low cost biofilters which consists of a bed of random or modular media through effluent percolates, scrubber, sponges and bamboo charcoal. These are advantageous over the other bio-filter media as the surface will not clog up when used with a pre-filter which may happen as in the case of ceramic material with micropores. Sponges and scrubbers help removing floating matters (solid particles) present in water. The treated water can be used for domestic purposes such as washing of utensils and clothes, bathing, and flushing as well as agricultural purposes.

Keywords: bio-filter, microorganisms, chemical contaminants and physical contaminants

INTRODUCTION

Water is a fundamental source to our existence. As cities expand and population grows, the demand for water is rising. With the increase in population, there will be an increase in stress on sanitation and wastewater disposal system. The concept of three R's, i.e. Reduce, Reuse and Recycle is a part of cleaner production on pollution prevention at source rather than the end of pipe treatment. In other words, it is vitally important to treat wastewater in order to save a precious source and protect the environment from pollution. Water, a finite and indispensable resource, plays a pivotal role in shaping the world and influencing the dynamics of societies. However, the degradation of water quality has emerged as a significant global concern, impacting ecosystems, human health, and societal well-being. Improving the quality of water that is unfit for use in daily purposes is a challenging task. The benefits of a proper water treatment system is a basic necessity of a localities' well-being. Readily available materials and low maintenance in the design of filter is basic necessity for rural area.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Petter D. Jenssen and Lasse Vråle (2003) studied the treatment of Grey water using Aerobic Filter followed by Subsurface Horizontal Flow Constructed Wetland in Cold Climates. A combined vertical flow biofilter followed by a horizontal flow wetland filter is developed in the study. More than 70% BOD removal is possible in the single pass of biofilter using about 0.1m² surface area/person. For the combined biofilter/constructed wetland system the total area requirement is 1-3 m² person and the effluent meets European swimming water standards with respect to indicator bacteria and WHO drinking waterstandards with respect to nitrogen.

J. S. Lambe and R. S. Chougule studied Greywater Treatment and Reuse. In this study, a three-stage greywater filtration system at household level is constructed. Inlet PVC pipe of 63 mm, Inlet chamber with size 30cm x 30cm x 10cm of Brick masonry Cement plaster is constructed. Two treatment chambers are designed such as treatment chamber 1 with size 30cm x 60cm x 30cm is filled with gravels of size 40 to 60 mm and treatment chamber 2 with size

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

40cm x 60cm x 30cm filled with fine sand. Base of all the chambers are constructed with RCC. Outlet is provided through 63mm (2 inch) PVC pipe. Household greywater filtration system includes Sedimentation, Horizontal filter, Slow sand filter and disinfection process. After treating the grey water through this filtration system, it can be reused for Toilet flushing, Irrigation, floor washing and for construction purpose.

Objective: The main objective of the project is to prepare an effective, economic and portable bio-filter for rural localities.

Bamboo Charcoal: Bamboo charcoal is charcoal produced from plant matter and stored in the soil as a means of removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Bamboo charcoal is produced through a process called pyrolysis, in which bamboo is heated in the absence of oxygen. This process results in the decomposition of bamboo into charcoal while removing water and volatile organic compounds. Bamboo charcoal is known for its porous structure, which gives it a high surface area. This porous nature makes it suitable for various applications, such as water purification, air filtration, and as an ingredient in certain health and beauty products. Bamboo charcoal plays a crucial role in environmental sustainability. Derived from a renewable resource, bamboo, its production involves minimal environmental impact. With applications in water and air purification, bamboo charcoal contributes to eco-friendly solutions, promoting a healthier environment while addressing diverse needs from filtration to waste reduction.

Methodology: The easily available and natural materials used as filter media in the laboratory scale biofiltration unit such as sand, gravel, bamboo charcoal was collected. The bio-filter apparatus was made using sand, gravel, bamboo charcoal, sponges, nets, etc. The bed height of each material was determined and finalized by experimentation. The water samples were collected from JIST campus hostels for analysis. The filtration rate has been found out to be 20 ml/min. These samples are sent to the laboratory of Public health Engineering Department for analysis by standard method at laboratory for parameters such as pH, total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), hardness, Colour, odour. A few of the tests were performed by us in the laboratory such as alkalinity and pH test.

Collection of Samples: The water samples were collected from JIST campus hostels. Containers are filled with water, transported to the laboratory investigation of water before treatment and refrigerated. Maximum effort was taken to get the samples analysed within 24 hrs of the storage.

Bamboo Charcoal Production: Slow Pyrolysis was performed for about 30 minutes maintaining Temperature range between 300°C-350°C.

Materials Used: Filtration unit of 20 litres capacity, Sponges, Scrubbing Pads, Bamboo charcoal, Plastic net, Storing unit for treated water.

Advantages of Using Bio-Filter: This has the potential to be a replacement of the traditional sand gravel filter as these filters are very bulky and take up a lot of space. The amount of Iron decrease is significant and the cost of installation is very low. This filter can be used in remote rural areas where construction and installation of sand gravel filter can be trouble some. The treated water can be used for daily activities.

Design of Bio-filter: Four experimental setups were designed for water treatment and a water sample from each of these variable designs will be tested. The first arrangement contained only sponge and bamboo charcoal. The second and the third arrangements contained gravel and sand and a change in their layer thickness was made.

Photo Gallery:

Test Results:

Table1

Sl No.	Parameter	Unit	Desirable Unit	Maximum Desirable Unit	Result	
					Untreated Water	Treated Water
1.	Turbidity	NTU	1	5	5	3
2.	Odour	-	Agreeable	Agreeable	Agreeable	Agreeable
3.	Colour	-	Agreeable	Agreeable	Light Yellowish	Colourless
4.	Alkalinity	mg/L	200	600	140	100
5.	Hardness	mg/L	200	600	170	90
6.	Total Dissolved Solids	mg/L	500	2000	220	170
7.	Total Dissolved Solids	mg/L	25	1000	466.67	40
8.	pH	pH Units	6.5-8.5	No relaxation	6.8	7.2
9.	Iron Content	mg/L	0.3	No relaxation	0.88	0.39

CONCLUSION:

1. It was observed that Iron content and Chlorine content was decreased by a major
2. The pH units of the untreated was acidic and after treatment it was in the range of safe usable water.
3. The colour of the water samples turned colourless from light yellowish.
4. The Turbidity tend to decrease from 5 NTU to 3 NTU after treatment.

5. The alkalinity, hardness, Total suspended solids (TSS), Total dissolved solids (TDS) also tend to decrease from a higher unit to a lower unit after treatment.

REFERENCE

1. Vijaya V. Shegokar, Dilip S. Ramteke and Pravin U. Meshram(2015) “Design and Treatability Studies of Low-Cost Grey Water Treatment with Respect to Recycle Reuse in Rural Areas”,

- International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences.
2. Nirmala M.D, Muthukumar K, Ravikumar G. (2016) Grey Water Treatment Methods”, International Conference on Current Research in Engineering Science and Technology (ICCREST).
 3. Ukpong E.C, Agunwamba J.C.(2012) “Grey Water Reuse for Irrigation” International Journal of Applied Science and Technology.
 4. M.E. Moges, F.E. Eregno, A. Heistad, “Performance of biochar and filtralite as polishing step for on-site greywater treatment plant”, *Manag. Environ. Qual.* [
 5. Hossain, M. Bhuiyan, B. Pramanik, N. Sabzoi, G. Griffin, (2020) “Waste materials for wastewater treatment and waste adsorbents for biofuel and cement supplement applications: a critical review” *J. Clean. Prod.* 255
 6. R. Molaei (2014) “Pathogen and Indicator Organisms Removal in Artificial Greywater Subjected to Aerobic Treatment” Master thesis, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala
 7. Y.M. Patil, G.R., Munavalli(2016) “ Performance evaluation of an integrated on-site greywater treatment system in a tropical region” *Ecol. Eng.* 95
 8. Z.M. Yaseen, T.T. Zigale, D.R.K. Tiyasha, S.Q. Salih, S. Awasthi, T.M. Tung, N. AlAnsari, S.K. Bhagat (2019) “Laundry wastewater treatment using a combination of sand filter, bio-char and teff straw media” *Sci. Rep.* 9
 9. J.Padron-Paez, S. Almaraz, A. Roman-Martínez(2020) “Sustainable wastewater treatment plants design through multi objective optimization” *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 140
 10. A.D. Mande, B. R. Kavathekar, A. S. Langade, N. G.Lasankute, S. H. Patle (2018) “Low- Cost Household Water Treatment Systems: A Review” *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology(IJERT)*
 11. Ahmed Salah Eldin Shiba, Mohamed N. Ali (2020) “Grey water treatment, reused and benefit of the heat capacity of water to improve the environmental performance of internal space” *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume XII*
 12. Assayed A, Chenoweth J, Pedley S (2015) “Assessing the efficiency of an innovative method for onsite greywater treatment: Drawer compacted sand filter A case study”. *Ecological Engineering, Volume 81, Pages 525-533.*
 13. Batool H. Ibraheem, Musa Habib Alshammari, Husam H. Alwan (2019), “Evaluation of grey water treatment with pilot filter for irrigation purposes” *International Conference on Engineering Sciences, Materials Science and Engineering 671.*
 14. Deepika mandel, Pawan Labhasetwar, Shankar dhone, Ajay Shankar dubey, gagadharshinde, satishwate. (2011) “Water conservation due to greywater treatment and reuse in urban setting with specific context to developing countries”. *Asian Journal of Science and Applied Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1,PP 5-9*
 15. Dilip M Ghaitidak, Kunwar D Yadav (2014) “Characteristics and treatment of greywater a review”, *Environmental science and pollution research International, Volume :2 pp. 795-809.*

HOW TO CITE: Dr. Pranab Jyoti Barman*, Rhishikesh Gogoi, Muktar Ali, Wasim Zafar Islam, Design and Treatability Studies of Low-Cost Bio Filter In Water Treatment, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (3), 21-24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14953235>